

Boosting data interoperability of GoTriple.eu

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Introduction

GoTriple (<https://gotriple.eu>) is a multilingual discovery platform for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), whose development started through the TRIPLE [1] EU funded research project in 2019. It is a central hub for SSH researchers to find, access and reuse research artefacts such as “Documents”, an umbrella term that includes articles, publications, books, datasets and many other typologies of content types, “Projects” and the “Profiles” of authors. Released online in 2022, the platform has significantly grown over time and now includes over 19 million document metadata from multiple sources (about 1,500), including large aggregators (BASE, DOAJ, OpenAire, Isidore) and national repositories (German National Library, Hrčak, Biblioteka Nauki, ZRC Sazu, EKT, Recyt or Pombaline), together with over 25 thousand project descriptions and 23 million authors’ profiles.

Purpose

The primary objective of GoTriple is to enhance the accessibility and interoperability of research data in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). Since the very beginning, the platform has adhered to the FAIR principles, ensuring maximum content reuse by exposing data through open APIs which return results in open formats. A key element in this process is the GoTriple data model, formalized through the TRIPLE Ontology, designed to maximize semantic interoperability. This ontology was developed in compliance with semantic standards and with the explicit aim of establishing connections with well-known ontologies, controlled vocabularies, and external entities, ensuring resource reusability and maximum interoperability.

This work focuses on the evolution of this process, with particular attention to the strategies adopted to ensure extended access to GoTriple data. This need is driven by the organic growth of the platform, not only in terms of indexed content but also of visits, active searches, registered users, and, most importantly, of new research initiatives that support the development of new features. This analysis will explore the challenges and solutions implemented to expand and integrate GoTriple data’s interoperability, fostering knowledge sharing and data reuse within the SSH research ecosystem.

Methods

The ongoing work to enhance GoTriple’s data interoperability draws on a combination of ontology refactoring, semantic mapping, and iterative alignment with emerging standards. In particular, two major EU-funded research projects, ATRIUM and GRAPHIA, provide both the context and the means for refining and expanding the TRIPLE Ontology.

First, the ATRIUM project [3] has been instrumental in guiding a large-scale refactoring of the TRIPLE Ontology, to improve how GoTriple models and exposes research information. This refactoring initiative, which continues until 2027, addresses multiple aspects:

1. **Broader Coverage of Entities:** the previous version of the TRIPLE Ontology focused on “Documents” and related elements such as “Document types,” “Disciplines,” and “Licenses.” Through ATRIUM, the ontology now formally includes the other two major GoTriple entities, “Projects” and “Profiles”, thus enabling a more complete representation of the research lifecycle and the network of relationships among authors, projects, and publications.
2. **Semantic Alignment with Established Vocabularies:** ATRIUM devotes a specific task (T3.1 “Semantic Interoperability”) to harmonize the TRIPLE Ontology with well-known domain standards and controlled vocabularies. For instance, the ontology’s “Document types” align closely with the COAR Controlled Vocabularies for Repositories [4], ensuring consistent categorization of research outputs such as articles, books, or datasets. Similarly, the “Disciplines” modeled according to the SKOS ontology, are mapped to external classification systems (e.g., Library of Congress Subject Headings, Dewey Decimal Classification) and linked data repositories like Wikidata.
3. **Mapping to Upper-Level Ontologies:** In keeping with ATRIUM’s priority to foster broad interoperability, the TRIPLE Ontology is being aligned with upper-level ontologies such as CIDOC CRM [5] and SSHOCro [6]. While CIDOC CRM offers a robust framework for cultural heritage and museum data, SSHOCro provides a disciplinary reference model tailored to the Social Sciences and Humanities.

Second, the GRAPHIA project [7] offers a complementary perspective, aiming to build a specialized knowledge graph for the Social Sciences and Humanities. Although GoTriple currently employs a search index rather than a graph database, its entities are already richly interconnected and can be exported in graph formats. This makes GoTriple a natural candidate for integration into GRAPHIA's SSH knowledge graph. As GRAPHIA advances (2025 - 2027), it will utilize GoTriple's data structure to create a more comprehensive graph, and in turn, graph-based insights could guide further refinements of the TRIPLE ontology. The starting point for this integration can be the Scientific Knowledge Graphs – Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) [8]. SKG-IF proposes a metamodel that facilitates continuous exchange between research knowledge graphs, with active participation from initiatives such as OpenAIRE and OpenCitations.

All efforts in redefining and extending TRIPLE's ontology are based on the Simplified Agile Methodology for Ontology Development (SAMOD) [10], ensuring that changes to the ontology undergo iterative cycles of design, implementation, and review. This agile process is well suited to collaborative and large-scale projects, allowing for regular feedback from both developers and domain experts. Each iteration involves documenting ontology evolution and verifying alignment through integrations or test mappings.

Results

The refactoring of the TRIPLE Ontology under ATRIUM has formalized Documents Types, Projects, and Profiles, ensuring alignment with standards like COAR Controlled Vocabularies,

CIDOC CRM, and SSHOCro. This enhances metadata consistency and facilitates integration with Open Science infrastructures.

Although still in its early stages, the alignment between GoTriple and the SKG-IF metamodel already indicates clear, straightforward mappings for the core entities. Focusing on GoTriple's primary asset, the "Documents" ontology reveals a simple way to match its classes to those in SKG-IF's "Research product," which includes "ScholarlyWork" and "Dataset." These classes readily accommodate the main types of GoTriple content.

Similarly, GoTriple's "Profiles" can be mapped to SKG-IF's "Agents," with the further option to specify roles (e.g., "author" or "editor"). However, mapping the "Projects" from the TRIPLE Ontology presents a greater challenge. The closest match within SKG-IF appears to be the "Grant" ontology, which applies to most GoTriple projects, particularly those imported from the European Commission's CORDIS [9] service, but may not fully capture unfunded initiatives. GoTriple encompasses in fact not only projects funded by grants or other schemes but also, in a few cases, citizen science initiatives in SSH disciplines that rely entirely on voluntary work and thus have no funding.

Value

By enhancing GoTriple's semantic interoperability, the platform improves discoverability, reuse, and integration within Open Science. The refactored TRIPLE Ontology ensures consistency across platforms, making SSH research more accessible. Aligning with SKG-IF and GRAPHIA will strengthen GoTriple's role in research knowledge graphs, facilitating cross-platform data exchange.

These efforts support emerging research needs, enabling better representation of publication types, authorship, and funding, while fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. The agile, iterative ontology development ensures sustainable growth, confirming the role of GoTriple as a scalable, FAIR-compliant infrastructure for SSH research.

References

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